

**RESEARCH ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN APRACIAB MURALS AND
KOREA - FOCUSING ON THE SOLIDARITY OF THE 7TH CENTURY GOGURYEO
ENVOYS AND THE POSSIBILITY OF EXCHANGES BETWEEN SILLA, BAEKJE,
AND BALHAE**

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Abstract. *Uzbekistan is one of the countries in the former Soviet Union, along with Kazakhstan, where a large number of Koryo people live. Since the 1990s, many Uzbeks have been exposed to the Korean Wave or have gone to Korea to work, so the perception of Korea in Uzbekistan is relatively good.*

It was revealed through the murals of Goguryeo's Afrasiab Palace that Goguryeo interacted with the Sogdian-Turks in Afrasiab near Samarkand. The most likely theory is that it was an envoy dispatched by Yeon Gaesomun in the mid-7th century to conclude an alliance to keep the Tang Dynasty in check. It is assumed that Goguryeo envoys at that time went to Afrasiab via the northern grassland road.

The Sogdians who stayed in Balhae played an important role in exporting Balhae horses to the Tang Dynasty. Unified Silla was established around the 8th century when Hyecho, a monk from Silla and the author of <Wango Cheonchukguk>, traveled all the way to present-day Iran. His stops included Samarkand and several other cities in present-day Uzbekistan.

We need to devise a win-win strategy by reviving the ancient historical exchanges between Korea and Uzbekistan through the 21st century Korean Wave.

Keywords: *Korea, Uzbekistan, Goguryeo, Afrasiab murals, Korean Wave contents, international exchange.*

1. Introduction: History and exchange between Korea and Sogd in the 7th century

In the 7th century, Korea had Goguryeo, Baekje, and Silla, and Silla united with China's Tang Dynasty, destroyed Goguryeo and Baekje, and became the unified Silla. In the former Goguryeo region, there was a country called Balhae.

In the 7th century, two people who are presumed to be Goguryeo people appear in Aprasiab murals. Generally speaking, they are seen as Goguryeo people, but many scholars have opinions on exactly when and for what purpose they came.

I would like to summarize the research on the Aprasyap and Sogdians of 7th century Uzbekistan in Korea and suggest future research directions.

2. When did the Goguryeo envoy visit?

<West wall restoration map>

For what purpose did the Goguryeo envoy 'Jowoogwan' go to Afrasiab? When will that time be? China (Tang), which destroyed Baekje in 660, attempted to destroy Goguryeo in order to establish a China-centered world order.

Thus, Tang began a war with Goguryeo in April 661 and besieged Pyeongyang Fortress for seven months from August to March of the following year, 662. In September 661, Gyepilharyeok's army fought and won against the army of Namsaeng, the son of Yeon Gaesomun, in the Yalu River basin.

In response to this crisis, Yeon Gaesomun (淵蓋蘇文) requested troops to be dispatched to Japan and attempted to overcome the crisis through an alliance with Cheorleuk (鐵勒), who was rebelling against the Tang at the time.

At this time, the Goguryeo envoy dispatched to Cheolreuk was the 'Jougwan envoy' depicted in the mural at the Afrasiab Palace. It can be assumed that the 'Jowoogwansajeol' departed from Goguryeo and went to Cheolreuk around February 662, when Sujeongbang's navy temporarily lifted the siege of Pyeongyang Castle.

It can be estimated that the envoy Jo Woo-gwan went to Samarkand around June 662 or April 663, approximately three months after leaving Cheolreuk. Accordingly, the period when the 'Envoy Envoy' was painted on the mural at the Afrasiab Palace began around June 662 or April 663, when the Envoy Envoy entered Samarkand, the last year of the reign of King Barhuman of Samarkand. It can be estimated to date to 675.

3. The relationship between the contents of the Afrasiab Palace murals and 7th century Korea

3.1. Is this a mural from the era of King Bahuruman?

There are various views on the main character of the western wall depicting the Goguryeo envoys, including King Barhuman, the King of Turks, or the Heavenly God of Zoroastrianism. Additionally, the relationship between the southern wall and the northern wall was initially recognized as a wedding mission, but many interpretations took into account the deities and religious rituals of Zoroastrianism that were prevalent in the Sogd region.

In particular, the procession on the south wall was considered a ritual on the 6th day of Norz, a traditional New Year ritual, and correspondingly, the Chinese Dragon Boat Festival event that coincided with Navruz was depicted on the north wall.

Meanwhile, the general opinion was that the composition of the four walls depicted the four countries (or kings) of the surrounding great powers centered on Samarkand.

3.2. Is the Goguryeo envoy a real person?

Next, various opinions were developed about the Goguryeo mission, including the nationality controversy, the reason why the Goguryeo people went to Samarkand, the route the mission took, and whether it was an actual mission or a symbolic image.

Is the Goguryeo delegation depicted in the Afrasiab mural the actual Goguryeo seen by the Sogdians, a copy of a painting brought in from China, or a Sogdian drawing of an image of the Goguryeo people?

However, since the mid-4th century, paintings presumed to be rituals such as Hoseonmu and Somakcha, traditional dances of Sogd, have been discovered in Goguryeo tomb murals. It seems that direct exchanges between the Sogdians and Goguryeo were already active at this time.

Meanwhile, there is also a possibility that glass vessels and Sassanian silver vessels excavated from the Silla tombs around the mid-5th century were introduced through direct exchanges with the Sogdians, who were the main players in East-West trade.

Old Korea and Sogd, Uzbekistan, had a deep relationship with Sogd, as seen in archaeological artifacts. We have called Sogd and its people 'Western elements' or 'Western people.'

4. Conclusion: Exchange cooperation and research direction between Korea and Uzbekistan

In 2019, Korea's Cultural Heritage Administration and Uzbekistan's Ministry of Culture are creating new opportunities for exchange by signing a memorandum of understanding for cultural heritage official development assistance projects. In line with these changes of the times, there is a need to study the culture of old Sogd in depth through the study of the Afrasiab murals, which were old ruins in Uzbekistan.

As a future research task, we will need to deeply examine Zoroastrianism and ritual traditions, which are elements of the interpretation of the Afrasiab murals.

If we reveal how Zoroastrianism, which emerged in Iran, influenced Sogd's culture and art, and what Sogd's unique elements are, the content of the palace murals will become more concrete.

In addition, although much research has been done on the Sogdians as traders, their role as cultural spreaders also needs to be paid attention to. In order to understand the Sogdians as cultural spreaders, it is necessary to study Sogd-related art not only in Sogdiana but also in various regions along the Silk Road connecting East and West.

The Sogdians and their culture have their own unique traditions. So far, Korea has been very interested in Chinese-centered art culture, but does not fully understand the culture of the nomadic peoples of Central Asia. The culture of nomadic peoples in each region actually influenced China and brought about changes in China's art culture. In the future, the influence of Sogdian artistic and cultural elements on Chinese art will need to be revealed one by one.

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